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**FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE PITUITARY-THYREOID-
TESTICULAR SYSTEM OF OFFSPRING OBTAINED UNDER
CONDITIONS OF EXPERIMENTAL HYPOTHYROIDISM IN FEMALES**

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Objective. The aim is to the identification of features of physiological development and formation of the endocrine status of male rats obtained under conditions of experimental hypothyroidism of pregnant females. **Materials and methods.** Hypothyroidism in female rats was induced by oral administration of the anti-thyroid drug Mercazolil at the rate of 0.5 mg per 100 g of body weight for 21 days. **The results.** It has been established that maternal hypothyroidism leads to a delay in physical development and a pronounced imbalance of the pituitary - thyroid - testicular system in their offspring. **Conclusions.** In female rats with experimental hypothyroidism, physiologically immature offspring are born, which is reflected in a decrease in the number of rat pups in litters, males, a decrease in the number of surviving rat pups, a slowdown in the accumulation of body weight after birth, and a longer preservation of signs of immaturity compared to the control group. Experimental hypothyroidism induced in females before pregnancy leads to a significant imbalance of the pituitary-thyroid and pituitary-testicular systems in the offspring.

Keywords: hypothyroidism of pregnant females, offspring, postnatal ontogenesis, physical development, pituitary - thyroid system, pituitary - testicular system.

The endocrine system is a set of interconnected structures that perform specific functions. The formation, development, and functioning of organs begin during intrauterine development and continue until physiological maturity; however, under the influence of endo- and exogenous factors, disturbances may occur not only in the functioning of the endocrine glands but also in the entire body, which subsequently negatively affects the reproduction of offspring [3;7].

One of the causes of perinatal pathology, including the birth of physiologically immature offspring, is extragenital disease of the mother, among which thyroid pathology is of particular importance. Among the pathologies of the thyroid gland, a special place is occupied by the so-called "maternal hypothyroidism" (hypothyroidism of pregnant women or gestational hypothyroidism), which in recent years has attracted increasing attention from researchers since a deficiency of thyroid hormones, necessary for the normal development and functioning of almost every cell of the human body, causes severe changes in all organs and systems without exception [12;14;19]. According to the literature, children of mothers suffering from hypofunction of the thyroid gland are lagging behind in physical development, often have abnormalities of the central nervous system [15;16], and are predisposed to the development of infectious diseases and sexual dysfunctions. It has been established that even subclinical forms of thyroid pathology in the mother can have an extremely adverse effect on the condition of the fetus and newborn [17;20].

Despite the widespread increase in the number of hypofunctions of the thyroid gland, the effect of maternal hypothyroidism on the physical development and hormonal status of the offspring in the dynamics of postnatal ontogenesis has been insufficiently studied.

The purpose of the study is to elucidate the characteristics of physical development and the formation of the endocrine status of rat pups obtained under conditions of experimental hypothyroidism in pregnant females.

Material and methods Hypothyroidism in female rats was induced by per os administration of the antithyroid drug Mercazolil at the rate of 0,5 mg per 100 g of

body weight for 21 days (experimental group). After establishing a stable decrease in the concentration of free thyroid hormones (T4 and T3), females were fertilized by healthy males. During pregnancy and lactation, females continued to be administered a maintenance dose of the drug at the rate of 0,25 mg per 100 g of body weight. A control group of females received an equal volume of sterile saline solution. The physiological maturity of the offspring of animals in the control and experimental groups was assessed by the number of live fetuses born, litter size, survival rates of animals during early postnatal ontogenesis (the first 7 days after birth), indicators of the dynamics of body weight growth, and also taken into account in each litter: opening of the palpebral fissures, unstickiness of the ears, appearance of primary and secondary coats, eruption of incisors, descent of the testicles into the pavement.

Hormonal status was studied in 14-, 21-, 30-, and 60-day-old rat pups obtained from healthy females and females with experimental hypothyroidism. After killing the rat pups, the blood was collected in dry, sterile tubes without anticoagulants, and the resulting blood serum was used to determine the concentration of hormones. Thyroxine (T4), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and testosterone in blood serum were determined by enzyme immunoassay using special kits from the company - Human (Germany) and a spectrophotometer - Single (Germany).

All digital data were processed using the variation statistics method. Calculations and statistical analysis were carried out using a statistical package for Windows. All data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The statistical significance of differences between the control and experimental groups was compared using the Student's t test, and P values <0.05 were considered significant.

Results and discussion. Currently, there is sufficient data indicating the important role of general physiological constants of laboratory animals, taking into account their gender and age characteristics, in assessing the influence of maternal extragenital pathology on the degree of their physiological maturity [1; 9; 13]. Based on this, we

analyzed the physiological development of the offspring of female rats with experimental hypothyroidism.

The study showed that in the offspring of female rats with hypothyroidism, the number of newborns in the litter decreased, so if in the control group the average number of pups in the litter was $8,9 \pm 0,6$ then in the experimental group this figure was significantly reduced and equal to $6,4 \pm 0,4$. In a comparative analysis of litters by sex, a decrease in the proportion of males in animals of the experimental group was noted; the ratio of female and male individuals in the litter in the control and experimental groups was 52,8:47,2 and 59,4:40,6 respectively.

In addition, the offspring of female rats with experimental hypothyroidism showed a decrease in vitality indicators. Thus, it was revealed that the proportion of rat pups that survived until the fourteenth day of postnatal development in the experimental group was 91%, versus 97.3% in the control.

According to modern concepts [1;8;21], a decrease in the dynamics of an animal's body weight gain during the early postnatal period is one of the signs of physiological immaturity. According to our data, animals in the experimental group showed a slowdown in the processes of body weight accumulation after birth compared to the control. The dynamics of studying the daily increase in body weight of rat pups showed that in the first 2 weeks after birth, the daily increase in body weight in rat pups of the control group was $0,98 \pm 0,06$ g, while in animals from females with experimental hypothyroidism this figure was $0,87 \pm 0,03$ g. In the period from the 15th to the 30th day after birth, the increase in body weight in rat pups of the control and experimental groups was $1,49 \pm 0,05$ g and $1,39 \pm 0,04$ g, and in the period from the 30th to the 60th day – $1,40 \pm 0,04$ and $1,27 \pm 0,07$ g, respectively.

Thus, the daily increase in body weight of animals in the experimental group during the period of postnatal development was significantly less than in rat pups obtained from healthy females.

Analysis of the timing of the onset of certain stages of physical development in experimental animals allowed us to conclude that in the rat pups of the experimental

group, some signs of physical development are delayed, namely the formation of such signs as the descent of the testicles into the scrotum, eruption of the incisors, opening of the eyes, and covering the body with secondary hair lagged behind the control by 3,7; 1,2; 1,7; 1;0 days, respectively, while the detachment of the auricle and the covering of the body with primary hair practically corresponded to physiological norms and did not differ significantly from the indicators of the comparison group.

Thus, analyzing the data obtained, we can conclude that female rats with experimental hypothyroidism give birth to physiologically immature offspring, which is reflected in a decrease in the number of newborns in litters, a decrease in the number of surviving rat pups, a decrease in the number of males, and a slowdown in the processes of body weight accumulation after birth and longer persistence of signs of immaturity compared to the control group.

Throughout a person's life, normal levels of thyroid hormones are a necessary condition for the harmonious functioning of the body. The thyroid gland plays an important role in the complex processes of intrauterine development: it participates in the implementation of compensatory and adaptive reactions of the fetus when environmental conditions change; thyroid hormones influence growth and ossification processes, and the formation of the central nervous system of the fetus [14;16;19].

Taking into account the above, the next stage of our research was to determine the formation of the hormonal status of rat pups born from healthy females and from females with experimental hypothyroidism.

The thyroid gland synthesizes thyroxine (T4), which is then converted into triiodothyronine (T3), a more active hormonal form, by the action of deiodinase enzymes.

Based on studies of total triiodothyronine (T3), free thyroxine (T4) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) in the blood, the thyroid status of the offspring was established in the dynamics of postnatal ontogenesis.

Analysis of the dynamics of thyroid hormones showed a wave-like nature of changes in their content in the dynamics of postnatal development, so in 1-day-old

newborn rat pups of the control group, the concentration of total T3 in the blood serum was the lowest compared to all other age groups. In 7-, 14- and 21-day-old rat pups, there was a significant increase in the concentration of this hormone by 23%, 20,5% and 13%, respectively, compared to the previous study periods. At 30 days, there was an insignificant decrease in T3 concentration compared to 21-day rats. The highest levels of triiodothyronine were observed in 60-day-old rat pups, but no significant differences were found between 30-day-old animals.

The same trend of changes in concentration in the dynamics of postnatal ontogenesis was found in the study of free T4. The content of free T4 in newborns, like T3, was the lowest compared to all other age groups. By the 7th, 14th and 21st days of life, the T4 level in rat pups became significantly higher by 20,7%, 22,7% and 14,5% compared to the previous observation periods. In 30-day-old rat pups, an insignificant decrease in T4 concentration was observed compared to 21-day-old animals. At 60 days of postnatal life, this indicator was the highest compared to all other age periods.

The dynamics of changes in the concentration of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) in the blood serum of rat pups in the period from their birth to two months of age tended to increase and the highest TSH concentration was detected on the 60th day after the birth of rat pups, which was 30% higher than in 30-day-old animals.

Thus, in newborn rat pups the lowest concentration of thyroid hormones was observed; a significant increase in them was detected on days 7-21 and 60 days after birth. The lowest concentration of thyroid and thyroid-stimulating hormones in newborns is apparently associated with an insufficiently formed pituitary-thyroid system and, accordingly, with insufficient functional activity of the thyroid gland. An increase in the concentration of T3, T4 and TSH in the early period of postnatal ontogenesis (7-21 days) may be associated with an increase in the proliferative activity of cells, intensive growth and development of organs and systems, a change in the nature of nutrition, a transition to definitive nutrition, which is consistent with Kuzminova's data A.S. et al. (2019). The increased content of thyroid hormones in the early postnatal period indicates their important role in regulating the growth and

development of the body. The increased formation of thyroid and thyroid-stimulating hormones in the body of two-month-old rat pups can be explained by puberty and functional restructuring of their body.

Studies conducted to study the influence of gestational hypothyroidism on the formation of the thyroid status of the offspring in postnatal ontogenesis showed that experimentally induced hypothyroidism in females before pregnancy led to a significant impairment of the thyroid function of their offspring. The concentrations of T3 and T4 in the experimental group during all periods of the study were significantly reduced compared to the control. The greatest difference in the concentrations of T3 and T4 was noted on days 14 and 21 after birth, when the level of hormones in experimental rat pups was more than 1,3-1,4 times less compared to similar data in the control group, while the decrease in the content of thyroid hormones was accompanied by an increase in the concentration of pituitary TSH.

In 60-day-old rats, the low level of thyroid hormones remained and the content of free T4 in experimental animals was 1,5 times less than in the control, which indicates a deep suppression of the hormone-forming function of the thyroid gland. In response to this, by feedback type, the pituitary TSH concentration increased 1,7 times, which can be considered as a compensatory reaction of the endocrine system in response to blockade of thyroid function.

The results obtained allow us to conclude that experimental hypothyroidism in females, caused before pregnancy, leads to dysfunction of the thyroid gland of their offspring in the form of primary hypothyroidism, which is expressed in a decrease in the concentration of thyroid hormones and an increase in thyroid-stimulating hormones. At the same time, despite the increased level of thyroid-stimulating hormone, hypothyroidism in rat pups persists until puberty.

It is known that thyroid hormones have a significant effect on the regulation of the process of spermatogenesis [10;18;20;23]. By type of feedback, the level of thyroid hormones affects the content of thyroid-stimulating hormone of the pituitary gland, and

this, in turn, can affect the liberins or statins of the hypothalamic nuclei. As a result, the entire hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid-gonadal system may change [2;4; 11; 22].

Considering the above, to determine the functional state of the pituitary-testicular system of rats obtained from females with experimental hypothyroidism on the 60th day after birth (after they reached puberty to exclude the influence of age-related changes in the testicles on the results of the study), the concentration of gonadotropic hormones and testosterone was determined.

Data on studying the level of gonadotropic and sex hormones showed that in experimental animals obtained from females with experimental hypothyroidism, the content of luteotropic and follicle-stimulating hormones decreased by 2-3 times compared to the control. As a result of this, a 3-4-fold decrease in testosterone content in the blood serum was noted in experimental animals.

Thus, the results of the study showed that experimental hypothyroidism induced in females before pregnancy led to a significant imbalance of the pituitary-thyroid and pituitary-testicular systems in the offspring, which was accompanied by a decrease in the concentration of thyroid, gonadotropic, sex hormones and an adaptive increase in the content of thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Conclusions:

1. Female rats with experimental hypothyroidism give birth to physiologically immature offspring, which is reflected in a decrease in the number of male rats in litters, a decrease in the number of surviving rats, a slowdown in the accumulation of body weight after birth and a longer persistence of signs of immaturity compared to the control group.

2. During the period of growth and puberty in rats, the function of the thyroid gland increases, which is expressed in an increase in the level of thyroid hormones in the blood serum.

3. Experimental hypothyroidism caused in females before pregnancy leads to a significant imbalance of the pituitary-thyroid and pituitary-testicular systems in the body of the offspring.

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